

Social Challenges of Covid-19 Pandemic in the Well-being of Hotel Employees in Cavite

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Abstract: The social challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic in the well-being of hotel employees in Cavite are the focus of this research. The purpose of this research is to determine the social impacts of COVID-19 on hotel employees' well-being and how that influences their work performance. This research also investigated whether there is a substantial difference in demographics, age, educational attainment, department, or rank/position. A research questionnaire used a 3-point Likert scale to ask hotel employees about the social challenges of Covid-19 in their well-being. The findings revealed the primary sources of social problems faced by these employees during the pandemic. All 15 factors were affecting employees' workplace pressures and performance, but among the factors, with a mean of 2.467, salary being provided by the company which equates to the job performed and promotes job security has the highest mean. The survey also revealed that respondents had been impacted by the pandemic, and the researchers were able to pinpoint the sources of their social difficulties.

Keywords: Social Challenges, Covid 19, Hotel, Pandemic, Well-being, Cavite.

1. INTRODUCTION

A social issue is described as any situation or behavior that harms a large group of individuals and is widely recognized as a condition or behavior that needs addressing (The University of Minnesota Libraries, 2015). It is a societal issue that has been identified as a barrier to society's optimal functioning. It is critical to recognize that not all occurrences in society are elevated to the level of social issues. The general people must acknowledge the issue as a problem and citizens and/or community resources can work together to solve or mitigate the situation (The Chapel, 2021).

The world's economy was completely shut down in 2020 because of the Covid-19 pandemic, according to UNWTO (2020). The COVID-19 issue continues to have an impact on how hotel companies operate. Businesses must make changes to their operations to ensure the safety and health and safety of their workers and guests (Goessling et al., 2020).

COVID-19 had a significant impact on many in the first half of 2020, and people's health and lives are at threat. Individuals who are already on the outside of society, suffer from sickness, poverty, racism, and other types of social injustices. Social isolation has grown, jobs have been lost, and some social benefits have been cut. Social workers have struggled to keep doing their jobs, trying to adapt and innovate to meet new demands and prioritize the most essential elements of their jobs (Banks, et.al, 2020).

Since the pandemic, there has been a significant impact on the hotel and tourism industry worldwide, affecting the performance of hotels, and altering the work of hotel employees and the customer experience. Many personnel couldn't go to their workplaces or fulfill their tasks due to travel restrictions, border closures, and quarantine precautions. A million jobs might be lost, according to the World Travel & Tourism Council.

The Covid 19-pandemic did not spare our country, and it had a significant effect on a few local sectors, including the hospitality sector. Since the lockdown started in March 2020, millions of Filipinos working in hotels across regions experienced job displacement, anxieties, and mental breakdowns.

Hotels should manage their employee's well-being by letting them focus on their physical, emotional, and mental health. Three minutes of mindfulness each day can have a significant impact on mental health, according to research conducted by The Journal of Management (2018).

The Department of Labor and Employment, enforced the development and implementation of mental health policies and programs in workplaces, highlighting the importance of fostering workers' wellbeing (DOLE, 2020). As stated in Book IV – Health, Safety, and Social Welfare Benefits, it is the responsibility of any employer to offer all essential support to guarantee that their employees receive proper and prompt treatment (DOLE, 2020).

In this light, the researchers explored how hotels in Cavite manage their employees' social well-being and assess the social challenges they faced amidst the pandemic. The main goal is to learn how they overcame these social challenges and managed their health during times of Covid pandemic and conduct a study that aims:

1. To identify the specific factors of Social Challenges that affect the well-being of hotel employees since the pandemic;
2. To determine the different challenges and issues the hotels in Cavite experienced when managing the well-being of their employees;
3. To assess the knowledge and experience of hotel employees regarding their work performance amidst the COVID-19; and
4. To examine and evaluate the social impacts of COVID-19 on hotel employees' well-being that affects their work performance.

The hospitality sector has already felt the negative impacts of the pandemic on its performance since it started. Travel bans, home quarantine orders, and social distancing rules have been critical global responses to control the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Researchers have addressed the specific social challenges that have affected hotel employees' well-being since the pandemic started and how their state of well-being affects their performance and it was determined using an online questionnaire.

The study sought answers to the following questions:

1. In terms of the following, what is the demographic profile of the participants?
 - a. age
 - b. civil status
 - c. gender
 - d. educational attainment
 - e. department
 - f. rank or position level
 - g. years of working
2. How do the Social Challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic affect the well-being of hotel employees?
3. What factors were affecting employees' workplace pressures and performance when the COVID-19 pandemic started?
4. How are hotel employees dealing with their well-being amidst the Covid-19 pandemic?
5. What recommended actions can be drawn from the study to improve the well-being of hotel employees?

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no significant difference in the evaluation of the respondents regarding the level of social impacts of the pandemic on their well-being when grouped in profile. The overall assessment of the effect on employees' workplace pressures and performance when the COVID-19 pandemic started is the same across groups.

RESEARCH GAP

The research aims to show how the pandemic can impact the well-being of hospitality sector people by collecting data from hotel employees in Cavite. The following are the elements of the study.

It will help to continue the knowledge of social challenges and employee well-being by evaluating the challenges of the pandemic, such as perceived job uncertainty and key variables affecting employees' mental, emotional, and physical health. It can guide the sector on how to handle employees during the pandemic, considering the performance of employees is now a key component in a hotel's success.

In the hospitality sector, where employees must connect with customers and provide services, employees' well-being should be valued. The pandemic had an impact on every business worldwide, with the hotel industry becoming one of the most affected.

It not only affected the people to not travel, but to stay in hotels, making the industry go downhill which caused social impacts that negatively affected the employees.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), the COVID-19 virus can cause a respiratory tract infection. Numerous hospitality businesses have temporarily closed because of local lockdowns, stay-at-home orders, travel and transportation limitations, and other strategies to flatten the COVID-19 spike (Bartik et al., 2020).

Coronavirus pandemic had impacts on hotel employee stress as mentioned in the study of Wong, et al. (2021). The study explored on how the pandemic affected the perceptions of occupational pressures and their consequences on hotel employees. It evaluated job engagement, commitment to the organization, employee performance, subjective well-being, and engaged conduct. According to the findings, job satisfaction and organizational commitment highly impacted job performance and prosocial behavior, but not the turnover intention. The idea to investigate hotel workers' perception of work pressures and their consequences as they have been influenced by social demographic and job-related factors is similar with the purpose and goal of the research study.

There is advice on how organizations can promote employee well-being, according to the Mayo Clinic of Wellbeing (2021). On this matter, the researchers agree that it allows finding ways to encourage employees to practice gratitude and preventive care. Create a more relaxed, pleasant workplace with flexible working hours for improved work/life balance. Mindfulness is a meditation where you try to keep your mind at the moment and not worry about what's going on around you. Mindfulness can help your employees be happier at work by helping to focus on the present rather than worrying about the future.

COVID-19 has a continuous impact on industry and consumers all around the world. Fear of job loss and financial difficulties are the consequences of government actions such as lockdowns (Zhang & et al., 2020). In correlation to that, there is a fear of rising unemployment and a lengthy issue in the private sector but has received more attention during the current pandemic (Mazza & et al., 2020). The fear of economic disaster is considered an innovative structure in the study and is characterized as an employee's perception of the chance of downsizing.

The stress of being unemployed and unable to find work, according to research, was the leading cause of depression. Those who work or are seeking a job are experiencing financial problems because of the prolonged economic crisis. Employees experience psychological distress and fear of losing their careers because of these challenges. Working people are suffering tremendously as a result of the economic crisis (Shoss Mindy & Tahira, 2012). This crisis idea may affect stress, anxiety, and attrition, and tardiness may harm employees' health (Di Fabio, 2017).

Therefore, the researchers carried out a study that focuses on the social difficulties caused by the Covid-19 epidemic in terms of the wellbeing of hotel employees in Cavite.

The purpose of the study is to ascertain the social effects of COVID-19 on the wellbeing of hotel employees and how that affects how well they perform at work. In light of the coronavirus pandemic, the study's findings will be helpful in creating an action plan to enhance the health and productivity of hotel staff.

Research Paradigm

The theoretical framework that researchers utilized in the study is the IPO Framework based on Bertalanffy's General Systems Theory as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

According to MSW Programs (2020), the study of how systems interact with each other in a bigger complex system. Regardless of the context to which it is applied, the entire idea of the theory is that the whole is greater than the sum of its parts.

Systems theory aims to explain and propose ideas about traits that emerge in complex systems but do not appear to arise in any system within the total. General Systems Theory explores how all the elements came together to create the system and how this led to a result that none of these properties could create without a change in their environment because it is useful when working on social changes, this system is acceptable for our study as a strategy. Working with social change requires a unique perspective and context, which general systems theory provides. A system works in harmony with its surroundings when it is balanced.

In the conceptual paradigm, Input includes Covid-19 protocols from the World Health Organization that were followed, allowing researchers to gain ideas on how the said virus affected workplace conditions, especially in hotels. The respondents' demographic profile and their opinion on this study are among the inputs. Managers' Supervisors, Rank, and File. The researchers will ask for their permission to take part in this study.

For Process, the researchers presented survey questions to the specified people online rather than face-to-face in Process, which is the second box of the diagram. This is to ensure that the researchers do not become infected with the virus and that all safety precautions are followed. The answers were gathered online, and the results were tabulated. The findings were presented in tables and graphs, and it was assessed using a three-point Likert scale. The hypothesis was tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to see whether there were any significant differences in the participants' responses.

The Output was to develop an action plan or program to address the social challenges of hotel employees as part of their preparation for the pandemic. The action plan was decided based on the survey's findings to promote the efforts and states of employees and the awareness of hotels in the COVID-19 pandemic.

3. METHODOLOGY

A quantitative research method was used in the study. Data collection and statistical methods are used to conduct a systematic study of phenomena. The sampling method applied to the study was convenience sampling. Only those who volunteered to take part in the study participated in the survey.

Quantitative research was the appropriate technique used in the study since the researchers collected data using online questionnaires. The research technique allowed the researchers to determine how many people think, act, or feel differently. To properly analyze the whole data sample, the traditional quantitative research design style used for this study was to ask each responder identical questions. The respondents were chosen based on their jobs at the hotel and given a list of questions to answer. Respondents who do not fit neatly into one of the major categories will have their precise responses noted and utilized in the research study's analysis.

Research Locale

The study was conducted solely in Cavite by the researchers. The research local of the study are employees of hotels located in Cavite because of their experienced challenges and changes in operations because of the Covid 19 pandemic. Furthermore, the researchers chose participants who lived close to their chosen research location because it would be more

convenient for the researchers given the pandemic situation. A total of sixty (60) volunteer respondents participated in the study. The study was conducted during the second-semester class.

Participants of the Study

Sixty (60) participants in the study were divided into three groups: twenty (20) Managers, twenty (20) Supervisors, and twenty (20) Rank and File employees from different hotels located in Cavite. The researchers believed that they were qualified to provide answers raised in the study and help the researchers achieve the objectives.

The selected participants were screened based on minimum qualifications: age must be between the ages of 18 and 60; must be at least a Tech-Voc graduate; must be currently employed in a hotel working either in the kitchen, housekeeping/laundry, front office, bar, and dining departments, and have held the job position of rank-and-file, supervisor and manager for at least a year and up to 13 years.

Research Sampling

The researchers used convenience sampling which is also known as an "accidental sample". These samples are geographically or operationally near where the researcher is collecting data. Convenience sampling (also known as Accidental Sampling) is a sample distribution or technique where participants are included in the study if they fulfill criteria, such as accessibility, geographic location, availability at the time, or desire to cooperate. This method is affordable, and the subjects are easily accessible.

The main objective of this sampling is to gather information from individuals who are easily available for the study. The chosen respondents were those who were most appropriate for the research topic, thus the researchers opted to move forward with them after a careful analysis. Additionally, the respondents were able to provide specific, first-hand accounts of their experiences working in hotels during the pandemic.

After careful consideration, the researchers decided to move forward with the chosen respondents who were kind enough to volunteer and since they were the ones most appropriate for the study's subject. Additionally, the respondents were able to provide specific, real-world examples of their work in hotels that may be relevant to our study.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used in the study to determine the level of Social Challenges of Covid-19 impacting business operations guided by the 3-point Likert scale. The main objective of Wong, Kim, et al. study in 2021, from which the questionnaire was adapted, was to determine how the pandemic altered perceptions of occupational pressures and their effects on hotel personnel. It assessed workers' commitment to their jobs, organizational commitment, performance, subjective wellbeing, and engaged behavior. After a thorough evaluation, the researchers later changed it. It was also revised by the researchers after thoroughly assessing. The adviser reviewed the questionnaire for approval before the survey questionnaires were distributed to the respondents.

The questionnaire was divided into two parts by the researchers. The demographic profile of the respondents was determined in the first part of the survey questionnaire, which includes gender, age, position level, educational level, and years of experience.

The second part of the survey questionnaire contains questions per category that the respondents answered by determining the level of social challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic in their well-being as hotel employees by using the Likert scale to measure their opinions or attitudes on a range of topics. Among the concerns mentioned are hospitality stresses, inconsistent and demanding hospitality pressures, unethical work-borne stressors, and many other Covid-19-related limitations that have already harmed hotel personnel. The researchers devoted their time, effort, and collaboration to producing questions that use clear and plain language to reach the desired respondents.

The 3-point Likert scale was utilized in assessing and measuring this study as shown in Table 1. The mean range of 1-1.49 has a verbal interpretation of Slightly Affected (SA); while 1.50-2.49 has a verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA); and 2.50-3.00 Highly Affected (HA).

Table 1. Likert Scale

Numbers	Mean Range	V.I. Code	Verbal Interpretation
1	1-1.49	SA	Slightly Affected
2	1.50-2.49	MA	Moderately Affected
3	2.50-3.00	HA	Highly Affected

Data Gathering Procedures

Most of the researchers' related literature and studies were gathered from the internet, research papers, journals, books, and thesis papers. Sixty (60) personnel were selected as respondents. After a thorough analysis, the researchers decided to proceed with the selected respondents as they were the ones best suited for the research topic. Also, the respondents were able to give concrete and real-life experiences about working in a hotel during the pandemic.

The respondents were grouped according to rank or position: Managers, Supervisors, Rank and File, Receptionists. A total of sixty (60) respondents volunteered and took part in the study. The survey was conducted online through Google Form type of questionnaire using appropriate questions adapted from the study of Wong, Kim, et al. (2021) and their main goal of their study was to see how the pandemic affected the perceptions of occupational pressures and their consequences on hotel employees. It evaluated job engagement, commitment to the organization, employee performance, subjective well-being, and engaged conduct. The respondents were provided via the URL provided by the researchers. The level of COVID-19 social impact on the well-being of hotel staff was measured using a Likert scale. The researchers compiled and tabulated the data using MS Excel once the questions had been completed.

Data Treatment and Statistical Analysis

The data gathered from this research instrument were collected and organized according to the answers responded by the participants and were tabulated using the frequency approach by percentage and the means to generate the total number of responses. Tables and figures were used to present these findings. To determine the level of impact, the means per variable (well-being) was computed and analyzed using the 3-point Likert scale. The same data were analyzed statistically by applying one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to see if there are significant differences in the responses of the respondents when grouped in profile.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the data gathered, as well as the demographic profiles of the respondents, are presented in this portion of the study in percentages and weighted mean. The research also investigated whether there is a substantial difference in demographics, age, educational attainment, department, or rank/position.

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Figure 1. Age of the Respondents

Figure 1 shows that the age group of 41-50 was the most affected by Covid-19 pandemic in terms of physical and mental health. The said age group constitutes 36.7% of the total respondents of the study.

Figure 2. Civil Status of the Respondents

Figure 2 shows that married respondents have the highest frequency and percentage with a total of 46.7% whose physical and mental wellbeing were affected by Covid-19 pandemic.

Figure 3. Educational Attainment of the Respondents

Figure 3 shows that 61.7% of the respondents graduated with a bachelor's degree. It implies that the hotels who hired the said respondents had established an educational requirement among its employees to do tasks involved in hotel operations.

Figure 4. Department of the Respondent

Figure 4 shows the different departments of the hotel organization that were affected with the social challenges of the pandemic with an equal percentage of 20%.

Figure 5. Rank or Position Level of the Respondents

The data reveals that respondents have an equal percentage from each position which is 33.3%. This results from the number of respondents who works in the hospitality industry based on their job position which is 20 respondents per position level.

Figure 6. Years of Working of the Respondents

According to the respondents' years of work experience, Figure 6 shows their demographic profile. 20% of respondents were hotel employees with 1-3 years of experience in the hotel industry. 30% of respondents were hotel employees with 4-6 years of experience. The majority of the respondents with 31.7% are 7-9 years. 11.7% of respondents were hotel employees with 10-12 years. And the least with of the respondents with 3.3% are 13 years and above.

1. Level of Social Challenges of Covid-19 in terms of perceptions that affected the well-being of hotel employees

Table 1. Level of Social Challenges of Covid-19

Social Challenges Of Covid-19	Mean	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
[Employment Discrimination (Insecurity about the job, low skilled labors)]	2.88	HIGHLY AFFECTED
[Performance Issues & Community Gap (low productivity in work, inappropriate behaviors, etc.)]	2.38	MODERATELY AFFECTED
[Mental Breakdown (hopelessness, depression, social isolation, etc.)]	2.53	HIGHLY AFFECTED
[Unhealthy Lifestyle Change (or eating patterns)]	3.32	HIGHLY AFFECTED
[Transportation Difficulties]	3.88	HIGHLY AFFECTED
OVERALL MEAN	3	HIGHLY AFFECTED

Table 1 shows the social challenges that the respondents have ranked based on their experiences throughout the pandemic. Variables 2 have the verbal interpretation of moderately affected while 1,3,4,5 got the verbal interpretation of Highly Affected.

Social challenges relate to issues hotel staff have while interacting with people in society or engaging in typical social behaviors. Any condition or conduct that has negative implications for many people and is widely recognized as a condition or behavior that needs to be addressed is referred to as a social issue. Difficulties with an average mean of 3.9. The other highly affected variable is Unhealthy Lifestyle with a mean result of 3.3. The next highly affected variable is Employment Discrimination which has an average mean of 2.9. The last highly affected variable is Mental Breakdown of 2.5 mean. The variable that was moderately affected which is Performance Issues, results with an average mean of 2.4. The overall mean of the table one is 2.998 OR 3 with verbal interpretation of Highly Affected.

Table 2. Factors that were affecting employees' workplace pressures and performance

Factors were affecting employees' workplace pressures and performance	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Social interaction and effective communication through departmental meetings (social ties, networks, etc.).	2.38	Moderately Affected
2. Learning new tasks or technology through available training programs.	2.48	Moderately Affected
3. Employees are recognized because of excellent job performance.	2.45	Moderately Affected
4. Employees are recognized because of excellent job performance.	2.45	Moderately Affected
5. Incentives are given to employees based on job performance.	2.22	Moderately Affected
6. Leave with pay (sick, vacation, birthday, maternity, paternity, etc) is implemented to avoid .work burnout..	2.33	Moderately Affected
7. Allowances such as meals and transportation are provided.	2.03	Moderately Affected
8. Employees are allowed to further education if they want to	2.10	Moderately Affected
9. Counseling is provided to employees to relieve stress from work.	2.20	Moderately Affected
10. Work environment is maintained clean, safe and organized to facilitate better job performance.	2.35	Moderately Affected
11. Work hours is flexible to promote a balance between work and home duties.	2.38	Moderately Affected
12. Salary provided by the company equates the job performed and promotes job security.	2.37	Moderately Affected
13. Employees experiencing job Insecurity and fear of unemployment	2.33	Moderately Affected
14. Mental health or well-being issues, depression, hopelessness, and etc.	2.38	Moderately Affected
15. Changes in physical health negatively (tiredness, insomnia, obesity, etc.)	2.33	Moderately Affected
OVERALL	2.32	Moderately Affected

In Table 2, it shows the mean and verbal interpretation based on the different factors affecting employees' workplace pressures and performance.

There are a total of fifteen factors in this study which the respondents have selected from highly, moderately, and slightly affected. Some factors that the researchers have included are such as social interaction and effective communication through

departmental meetings (social ties, networks, etc.), learning new tasks or technology through available training programs, employees are recognized because of their excellent job performance, employees are recognized because of excellent job performance, incentives are given to employees based on job performance, employees are allowed to further education if they want to, counseling is provided to employees to relieve stress from work, and etc.

According to the data, the overall verbal interpretation of the factors has moderately affected the hotel employees. All 15 factors were affecting employees' workplace pressures and performance, but among the factors, with a mean of 2.48, learning new tasks or technology through available training programs has the highest mean. The second-highest mean is a total of 2.45 wherein employees are affected in being recognized of their excellent job performance.

The third highest mean, which is 2.38, among the factors is the social interaction and effective communication through departmental meetings, work hours flexibility that promotes a balance between work and home duties, and Mental health or well-being issues, depression, hopelessness, and etc. Among the fifteen factors that affected the employees' workplace pressures and performance, the lowest mean is 2.03, allowances such as meals and transportation are provided.

The overall mean of the table two is 2.32 with verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected. Overall, the factors were moderately affecting the employees' workplace pressures and performances.

2. Significant Difference in the Overall Assessment of the effect on employees' workplace pressures and performance

Table 3. Overall ANOVA

Cases	ANOVA					Interpretation
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	
AGE	2.069	3	0.69	3.614	0.019	NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE
CIVIL STATUS	0.229	3	0.076	0.342	0.795	NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE
Highest Educational Attainment	0.214	3	0.071	0.318	0.812	NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE
Department	0.753	4	0.188	0.863	0.492	NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE
Rank or Position Level	0.065	2	0.032	0.145	0.865	NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE
Years of Working	0.67	4	0.167	0.762	0.555	NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE

In Table 3, The null hypothesis, according to the results, there are no significant differences in respondents' overall assessment when grouped. It is rejected by a P-value of less than 0.05. Since all p-values are higher than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

As a result, when the respondents are categorized according to demographic profile, highest educational attainment, department, rank and years of working, there generally isn't a discernible variation in their perception. According to the findings, there is no measurable difference between employees' overall assessments of the impact of workplace stress and performance according to the results. The overall assessment of the effect on employees' workplace pressures and performance when the COVID-19 pandemic started is the same across all groups.

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

The researchers have developed a plan of action to evaluate and consider potential solutions for these difficulties they identified in their research. The objective is to ascertain the social effects of COVID-19 on the wellbeing of hotel employees and how that affects how well they perform at work. The first step in taking action is to assess the transportation issues and work with the government to develop a plan of action. With the money it allocates, the government should use the transportation industry, particularly, to come up with a solution that would solve the transportation issues faced by hotel staff.

Eliminating the pressures that impact employees' workplaces and boosting the elements that influence performance should be done in order to address the issues that affected employees' workplaces and what improved their performance when the COVID-19 epidemic started. Specifically, sick pay, praise, and the wellbeing of hotel staff members. In order to foster better connections among coworkers, all employees, regardless of rank, should practice respect and cooperation.

To encourage hotel personnel to be upfront and honest about their physical needs and demands for rest, when necessary, hotel authorities should establish a comprehensive system of break requests and schedules.

For the hotel personnel to be happy with their earnings from their work and feel valued as members of the hotel while having fewer financial worries, the hotel authorities should also prioritize raising salaries in line with economic changes and improving perks. To increase employees' wellness, mental health, and everyday performance, it is crucial to regularly organize seminars and wellness checks among the workforce.

Hotel staff suffer from social issues differently from one another on different factors, which are essential to be acted upon. The staff's well-being is important to the hotel as it is the main asset to its growth. With the data gathered, the researchers carefully and thoughtfully made an action plan to assist the hotel and its staff in dealing with the social issues that hindered their performance.

One of the goals of this plan is to improve the well-being of the staff through the assistance of the hotel in sufficing their needs. In the data provided, the respondents were highly affected the most due to the salary provided by their employers, job insecurity and the fear of unemployment, and their work time. The top 3 factors are commonly associated together with their contract with the company, and this struggle affects their performance.

To achieve this, it will be a long-term investment of the company to its staff. Providing financial assistance and benefits will more likely motivate its staff to do their work properly as not many companies provide adequate salaries to their workers. The feeling of neglect from its management and lack of benefits affects their performance overall. These benefits and importance the management give to their staff are really important as these workers are human as well and making them feel part of a team in the company, gives them the feeling of success along with the company.

It also assures the workers that they will be treated well but not tolerate their wrong actions. Prioritizing their well-being also means taking importance to their physical and mental health.

Accommodating break requests and understanding the health concerns of the staff are good ways to keep them going. These breaks are also a part of work as these humans also benefit from resting and prevent possible health complications that hinder their work performance. These actions require time, money, and effort from the management officials of the hotels as these may affect the capital temporarily, but it makes up for good management and service provided by the staff, especially in this service-based industry.

To evaluate and understand that these actions took effect, the management can set up annual surveys among its staff to see any improvements that occur during their adaptation to better working conditions. The result can also be seen from the performance of the hotel and from the feedback of its clients. These adjustments to the working condition of the staff will definitely help and improve the well-being of the staff and will result in better performance and relationship of the staff to the company throughout the years.

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